

Literature & case study review on outcomes in payments for ecosystem services / compensation for ecosystem services (PES/CES) programmes

Examples of factors influencing payment for ecosystem services outcomes found in the literature review.

Examples in the table are coded positive/negative to indicate direction of impact on outcomes.

Alignment	Factor	Influence on outcomes				
		Institutional	Socio-cultural	Livelihoods	Target ES (or non-target environmental)	Feedbacks
Institutional alignment	Fit with cultures and practices of resource use			+ Enhance equity		
	Land tenure codification/formalization			+ Formalize communal property and ability to manage/sell environmental goods + Improve access to forest products		+ Enhance enrolment
	Institutionalize community land use planning	+ Enhance community capacity			+ Clarify payment for ecosystem services implementation	
	Embeddedness in local institutions and trusted intermediaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthen existing governance institutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve socio-cultural outcomes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increase social impact and support long-term investments 	+ Enhance effectiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhance trust, participation, and enrollment
Institutional misalignment	Land use restrictions, including tenure formalization, in conflict with existing and traditional land uses	- Undermine traditional institutions and IPLC decisionmaking power	- Reduce social cohesion	- Land scarcity - Increase land conflict	- (non- target) Intensify cultivation/ shorten fallow rotations	
	Conflicting policy incentives				- Weaken compliance	

	Weak local institutions/lack of capacity			- Inhibit benefit distribution and pro-poor targeting		
	Conflicting/ unclear property rights			- Complicate benefit distribution - Adversely impact Indigenous and women's rights	- Inhibit effectiveness	
	Countervailing external political economic forces & policy incentives				- Weaken compliance and effectiveness	
Value alignment	Presence of equity objectives, social co-benefits, recognition of cultural and relational values		• Improved social outcomes		+ Enhance effectiveness	+ Enhance enrolment
	Locally-relevant ecosystem services and associated social benefits			+ Enhance livelihood benefits	+ Enhance environmental outcomes	+ Enhance enrolment
Value misalignment	Inadequate/inappropriate compensation and benefit-sharing			- Livelihood costs	- Weaken compliance	- Weaken enrolment
	Monistic valuation (single ecosystem services)	- Disrupt traditional lifeways	- Loss of traditional knowledge	- Diminish food sovereignty	- (non-target) Loss of traditional practices supporting BD	- Weaken enrolment
Knowledge alignment	Integration of ILK			+ Enhance benefit sharing and equity	+ Enhance monitoring; incorporate traditional management	
Knowledge misalignment	Inadequate free, prior and informed consent		- Confusion/ deception about program and goals	- Carbon piracy/loss of land rights		- Weaken enrolment
	Standards/compliance-driven program design	- May not ensure FPIC	- Confusion/ deception about program and goals		- Fail to address drivers of land use change	- Weaken enrolment